

Life in the clouds of Venus:

The phosphine debate and its scientific, social, and psychological impact

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Abstract. We examine the phosphine on Venus debate using a multidimensional impact model covering scientific, social and psychological dimensions. We illustrate the results of the analysis with two spider diagrams.

Keywords. Phosphine, Venus, Social Impact, Extraterrestrial Life

1. Introduction

The potential for life on Venus has been envisioned (e.g. Grinspoon, 2003; Schulze-Makuch et al., 2004; Limaye et al., 2018; Morowitz & Sagan, 1967), however, no indication has ever been discovered until recently. In September of 2020, Dr. Jane Greaves and her international team published a paper in *Nature Astronomy* about their discovery of phosphine in the clouds of Venus (Greaves et al., 2020). Phosphine, a molecule associated with anaerobic environments on Earth, suggested potential biological or unknown chemical processes on Venus. However, the discovery faced immediate scrutiny and scepticism. In this article, we discuss the phosphine debate and its scientific, social, and psychological impact on humanity, using the multidimensional impact model for the discovery of extraterrestrial life proposed by Vidal (2015). We illustrate the model and its application to the phosphine debate with spider diagrams in Fig 1. and 2.

2. Empirical Dimensions

To determine the impact of the phosphine debate on Venus, we must first look at the ten dimensions characterising the potential lifeform discovered. In terms of (1) *Distance*, Venus is in the inner solar system, neighbouring Earth, which presents a higher impact than a distant discovery. The candidate microbial life form is simple on a (2) *Complexity* scale and expected to be small in (4) *Size*, similar to microorganisms that we know exist on Earth. Microorganisms are typically found in great (5) *Numbers*, and the detection of phosphine suggests that they are (6) *Alive*, as the relatively short atmospheric lifetime of the reactive gas phosphine would imply that it is being replenished continuously or was produced very recently.

The (7) *Clarity* of the discovery was low and rather hypothetical. Although it was recently suggested that the presence of phosphine in the atmosphere of a rocky planet is a promising indicator of life (Sousa-Silva et al., 2020), phosphine is found in the reducing atmospheres of giant planets (Bregman et al., 1975; Tarrago et al., 1992) and there may be some unknown chemical processes that can produce phosphine abiotically on Venus (Greaves et al., 2020; Sousa-Silva et al., 2020). Since we're dealing with a potential biosignature, the dimensions of (3) *Intent*, (8) *Communicative Intent*, and (9) *Knowledge of Us* are inapplicable. The inapplicability of these dimensions suggests a lower overall impact than a technosignature where such dimensions might be applicable. However, it is important to consider the potential (10) *Influence on us*. Since Venus and Earth are neighbouring planets and have both existed for long time scales, and Venus might have been habitable (e.g. Way et al., 2016), potential

Figure 1. Spider diagram of the dimensions of impact of the phosphine debate on Venus. Dimensions (1-10) describe the kind of extraterrestrial life. Details about the generic impact model, its dimensions and options are in (Vidal, 2015).

exchanges of material through lithopanspermia could have taken place. It is therefore possible that potential life on Venus and life on Earth could share a common ancestor.

3. Scientific Impact

The scientific impact of the phosphine discovery on Venus can be characterised first, by the (a) *Universalization of Knowledge* dimension, which would be low if the lifeform turns out to be very similar to known microorganisms on Earth, or high if it turns out to have a different make up and mechanics (e.g. no RNA, DNA, or ribosomes). The (b) *Speed of Discovery* has been relatively slow as it took time for independent teams to re-analyze the data, and of course the “discovery” remains in debate (Bains et al., 2021; Encrenaz et al., 2020; Lincowski et al., 2021; Snellen et al., 2020; Thompson, 2020; Trompet et al., 2021; Villanueva et al., 2021). Furthermore, it would take even more time to send a sampling mission to Venus to analyse and test such potential Venusian life. Despite checks from two independent telescopes, the (c) *Data Quality* and its processing was low according to many experts, and this was aggravated by the fact that the ALMA telescope had some mistakes in their data release that they had to correct. The (d) *Source of Discovery* is a biosignature, which is a kind of signature that is typically expected in the astrobiology community. If confirmed without return-sample missions, (e) *Our Knowledge* of Venusian life forms would likely be limited to existence.

4. Social Impact

The (f) *First Impression* of the discovery was positive as it was unanimously welcomed. Although many were sceptical and scrutinised the initial findings, it was overall a positive first impression and it did not cause chaos. At first, major media outlets like *CNN*, *BBC*, and *The New York Times* reported the discovery enthusiastically (Amos, 2020; Stirone et al., 2020; Strickland, 2020), however, as independent teams re-analyzed the data, new outlets, such as *Forbes* and *Wired*, covered the controversy and highlighted that the initial discovery has been disproven (Beall, 2020; Siegel, 2020). Despite the COVID19 pandemic, the (g) *Socio-Political Context* can be argued to have been stable with minimal impact on space sciences. The (h) *Dissemination of the News*, as often, was rather sensationalist. The authors of the initial paper

Figure 2. Spider diagram of the dimensions of impact of the phosphine debate on Venus. Dimensions (a-e) describe the scientific impact and dimensions (f-j) describe the social dimensions of impact. Details about the generic impact model, its dimensions and options are in (Vidal, 2015)

were careful when putting forth the possibility of life on Venus, but scientists complained that it was premature to even suggest this possibility (Siegel, 2020). The dimensions of (i) *World Philosophy* and (j) *Religion* are not easy to study, as they would imply data gathering on how various human groups with different world philosophy or religion did react to this news.

5. Psychological Impact

Psychological impact is also very difficult to study, as it would imply data gathering on an individual level across various human groups, which is why we do not attempt to draw a spider diagram for these dimensions. However, the subjective impact of finding life on Venus would be high for many scientists as Venus has not been seen as a promising target, and most of the attention and hope was geared towards Mars and icy moons. For such scientists, their (k) *Preconceptions of Extraterrestrial Life* would have been challenged. Discovering life on Venus (or Mars) may lead to major (l) *Worldview* changes, especially because the possibility of cross-contamination from or towards Earth could change our evolutionary theories of the origin of life on Earth. There might be a remote danger of a Venusian microbe impacting Earth’s ecosystem, for example, should we decide to make a return-sample mission and accidentally contaminate and dramatically affect Earth’s ecosystem. In such a scenario, the human (n) *Hierarchy of Needs* would be impacted at a basic level if it directly affects human health or the food chain supply. To further study a particular individual reaction to the discovery, the (m) *Developmental Stage*, (o) *Age*, and (p) *Personality* of that individual matters. The phosphine debate involves at least two major uncertainties: the actual detection of phosphine itself and the link between phosphine and life. Someone emotionally stable, flexible in their worldview, positively minded, and with high self-esteem would cope with the uncertainties much more easily than someone who is emotionally unstable, with a dogmatic worldview, negatively minded, and with low self-esteem.

6. Conclusion

The potential discovery of phosphine on Venus has had far-reaching impacts across scientific, social, and psychological dimensions. If life on Venus can be confirmed, this could

mean that life is common in the solar system, and it would not be far-fetched to argue that it is extremely common in the galaxy. This paradigm shift would challenge our fundamental understanding of life's distribution in the cosmos. Although not yet a confirmed discovery, the impact of the potential discovery is still seen as high because (1) the discovery is nearby and thus follow-ups are not only possible, but already planned (see e.g. the Venus Life Finder mission, French et al., 2022), (2) it has stimulated research, debate, and international collaboration, and (3) it has reignited the scientific community's curiosity, which had largely discounted the possibility of life on Venus. This phosphine debate is highlighting the need to study more systematically the potential presence of life in the solar system. With a renewed focus and the latest push in missions towards Venus, we are on the brink of potentially groundbreaking discoveries with higher levels of scientific, social, and psychological impact.

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